

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION

Anshika Verma*, Jyoti Verma, Dr. Sanjay Kumar Kushwaha, Priya Patel

Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceuticals Science and Research, Seewar, Sohawal-Ayodhya.

Article Received on 12 April 2026,
Article Revised on 02 May 2026,
Article Published on 10 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20121258>

*Corresponding Author

Anshika Verma

Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceuticals
Science and Research, Seewar,
Sohawal-Ayodhya.

How To Cite This Article: Anshika Verma*, Jyoti Verma, Dr. Sanjay Kumar Kushwaha, Priya Patel. (2026). A Comprehensive Study of Analytical Method Development And Validation. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 1651–1664. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical discovery, development, and manufacture depend heavily on the development and validation of analytical methods. As more medications are introduced to the market each year, it is necessary to create new analysis techniques for these medications. Following the development, the new analytical method needs to be validated. The process of demonstrating that an analytical method is suitable for usage is known as method development. Analytical method validation provides details on a number of phases and parameters, including accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection, limit of quantification, specificity, range, and robustness. Regulations like ICH rules should be followed when performing validation. This article was prepared with the intention of reviewing the development and validation of

analytical methods.

KEYWORDS: Analytical method, Spectroscopy, UV-VIS spectroscopy, Chromatography, HPLC, Method development, Validation.

INTRODUCTION

Analytical chemistry is a subfield of chemistry that focuses on identifying the qualitative and quantitative components of substances or samples or combination. There are two different kinds of analysis: qualitative analysis and quantitative analysis. Identification of mixture components or analytes is done in qualitative analysis sample is completed. The amount of components or analytes in a mixture or sample is determined in quantitative analysis (Kenkel

J, 2003). In addition to chemistry, other sciences including biology, zoology, the arts like painting and sculpture, archeology, space exploration, and clinical diagnostics also depend on analytical data. Clinical and biological studies, geological tests, quality control in industrial industries, monitoring and management of pollutants, and fundamental and applied research are all significant applications of analytical chemistry (Kissinger PT, 2002).

ANALYTICAL

When conducting a qualitative, quantitative, or structural examination of a sample for one or more purposes, an analytical method comprises the application of a particular methodology and comprehensive, step-by-step instructions. (Kissinger PT, 2002) analytes.

There are two primary categories of analytical methodologies: Instrumental and classical approaches (Figure 1). The term "classical method" refers to a technique where the signal is proportionate to the total amount of analyte. An instrumental approach is one where the signal is proportionate to the concentration of the analyte (Harvey D, 2000).

Figure 1: Classification of Analytical Methods.

Analyte separation, qualitative analysis, and quantitative analysis are the three primary categories of classical methods. Analyte separation involves filtering, precipitation, distillation, and extraction. Boiling point, freezing point, color, odor, density, reactivity, and refractive index are all included in qualitative analysis. Gravimetric and volumetric analyses are examples of quantitative analysis.

Spectroscopic methods, electrochemical methods, chromatographic methods, and other techniques are the four primary categories of instrumental methods. UV-visible spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy, and other spectroscopic techniques, Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic spectroscopy, x-ray spectroscopy, and atomic absorption and emission spectroscopy. Potentiometry, Coulometry, and Voltammetry are examples of electrochemical techniques.

Column chromatography, paper chromatography, thin layer chromatography, high performance liquid chromatography, gas chromatography, and contemporary techniques (LC-MS, GC-MS, LC-MS-MS, GC-MS-MS, LC-NMR, and GC-NMR) are examples of chromatographic techniques.

Additional approaches include mass spectrometry, radioactivity, x-ray methods, optical methods (refractometer, optical rotation), and thermal methods (differential thermal analysis, differential scanning calorimetry, and thermogravimetry) (Ravisankar P, et al., 2015; Jeffrey GH, 1989).

INTRODUCTION TO SPECTROSCOPY

The study of how electromagnetic radiation interacts with matter is known as spectroscopy. In these interactions, the matter absorbs and emits radiation, or energy. There are two forms of spectroscopy: emission spectroscopy and absorption spectroscopy. Absorption spectroscopy (UV-visible, IR, NMR, microwave, and radio wave spectroscopy) is the study of electromagnetic energy absorbed by the sample in the form of spectra. Emission spectroscopy (flame photometry and fluorimetry) is the study of electromagnetic radiation released by the sample in the form of spectra. Emission spectroscopy (flame photometry and fluorimetry) is the study of electromagnetic radiation released by the sample in the form of spectra. Spectroscopy is employed in the investigation of a variety of materials and is helpful for the research of atomic and molecular structure. Atomic spectroscopy, such as flame photometry and atomic absorption spectroscopy, is the study of how electromagnetic radiation interacts with atoms and how energy changes at the atomic level. Molecular spectroscopy, such as ultraviolet and infrared spectroscopy, is the study of how electromagnetic radiation interacts with molecules and how energy changes at the molecular level (Chatwal GR and Anand SK, 2002).

UV-VIS SPECTROSCOPY

The amount of light absorbed at each UV and visible wave length in the electromagnetic spectrum is measured in UV-visible spectroscopy. The ultraviolet (UV, 200–400 nm) and visible (VIS, 400–800 nm) bands of electromagnetic energy are used in this absorption spectroscopy (Kumar S, 2006).

The foundation of UV-visible spectroscopy is the absorption of visible or ultraviolet light by a chemical or material that leads to the creation of various spectra. Ultraviolet emission spectra result from the opposite kind of transition that occurs when a molecule absorbs UV radiation, which excites the electron within the molecule and leads it to go from a lower level to a higher electronic energy level. Water, methanol, ethanol, ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane, and dichloroethane are the most often utilized solvents in UV spectroscopy. Functional group, conjugation, geometrical isomer, and impurity identification are among the uses of UV spectroscopy (Chatwal GR and Anand SK, 2002).

INSTRUMENTATION OF UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY

A. Radiation sources: Tungsten lamps, hydrogen discharge lamps, deuterium lamps, xenon discharge lamps, and mercury arcs are the most widely utilized radiation sources (Figure 2).

Figure 2: UV-Visible spectroscopy.

B. Wavelength selector: Radiation is dispersed according to wavelength using a monochromator. An entrance slit, a dispersing element, and an exit slit are the fundamental components of a monochromator.

C. Sample cell: Cells or cuvettes are sample containers used in UV-visible spectroscopy to hold liquid samples. Quartz is used to make cuvettes.

D. Photo detector: The barrier layer cell, photocell, and photomultiplier tube are the most often used detectors in UV spectrophotometers.

E. Readout device: After being appropriately amplified, the detector's output is shown on a readout device (Chatwal GR and Anand SK, 2002).

INTRODUCTION TO CHROMATOGRAPHY

A physicochemical technique for separating mixtures of substances is chromatography. Chromatography is a technique that separates a mixture of chemicals into their constituent parts between a stationary phase and a mobile phase (Laxminarayan L, et al., 2017).

The following categories apply to chromatography

1. Depending on how the solute interacts with the stationary phase.

Chromatography by adsorption.

Partition chromatography.

Chromatography using ion exchange.

Molecular exclusion chromatography.

2. Considering the form of the chromatographic bed

Column chromatography.

Planar chromatography.

Chromatography on paper.

Thin layer chromatography.

Displacement chromatography.

3. Methods based on the mobile phase's physical state

- Gas chromatography
- Liquid chromatography
- Affinity chromatography (Laxminarayan L, et al., 2017).

HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY

High performance liquid chromatography, also known as high-pressure liquid chromatography, is referred to as HPLC. Any material that can be dissolved in liquid can have its chemicals separated, identified, and quantified using HPLC (Chawla G and Chaudhary KK, 2019). Adsorption is the fundamental idea of liquid chromatography. This chromatographic method uses a liquid as the mobile phase. The sample is a liquid solution. A column containing a liquid phase (mobile phase) and a porous substance (stationary phase) is filled with the sample. A pump's high pressure allows the sample to pass through the column with the mobile phase. The components of the sample move in the direction of the stationary phase based on their affinity. The component that is more attracted to the stationary phase moves more slowly. The component that is less attracted to the stationary phase moves more

quickly. The parts are kept apart from one another (Vidushi Y and Meenakshi B, 2017). n-hexane, methylene chloride, chloroform, methyl-t-butyl ether, tetrahydrofuran (THF), isopropanol (IPA), acetonitrile (MeCN or CAN), methanol (MeOH), and water are the most often used solvents for HPLC (McPolin O, 2009). Efficiency (number of theoretical plates), retention factor, selectivity, resolution, and pressure are basic chromatographic characteristics (Ravisankar P, et al., 2015). HPLC is used for chemical separation, purification, and identification. Pharmaceutical, environmental, forensic, therapeutic, food, and flavor applications are additional uses for HPLC (Figure 3). (Malviya R. and others, 2010).

Figure 3: HPLC system.

Instrumentation of HPLC

The HPLC system's components include:

- A. Solvent reservoir, mixing system and degassing system.
- B. High pressure pump.
- C. Sample injector
- D. Column
- E. Detector
- F. Data recording system

1. The mixing system, degassing system, and solvent reservoir: The solvent (mobile phase) is kept in a solvent reservoir. These are stainless steel or glass containers. Glass bottles are the most popular kind of solvent reservoir (Jena AK, 2011). The pump must mix solvents with extreme precision and accuracy in addition to delivering the mobile phase. Low pressure mixing and high-pressure mixing are two different kinds of mixing units (Agilent Technologies, 2016). Trapped air bubbles are eliminated from the solvent using a degassing device. Ultra-sonication and filtration are degasser techniques used for degassing (Jena AK, 2011).

2. High pressure pump: A pump's job is to force a liquid and provide a certain flow rate. Millilitres per minute (ml/min) is the unit of measurement for flow rate. 1-2 ml/min is the typical flow rate. According to Chawla G and Chaudhary KK (2019), the pump pressure range is 6000-9000 psi (400-600 bar). Constant pressure pumps, syringe pumps, and reciprocating piston pumps are often utilized types of pumps (Hamilton RJ, Sewell PA, 1982).

3. Sample Injector: The sample injector introduces the liquid sample into the mobile phase. The sample valve is located between the column and the pump (Jena AK, 2011). The sample can be injected into the continuous running mobile phase stream that transports it to the HPLC column using an injector (auto sampler). 5–20 microliters (μ l) are typical sample volumes (Chawla G and Chaudhary KK, 2019). Injectors come in two varieties: manual and automatic (Hamilton RJ, Sewell PA, 1982).

4. Column: The real separation of components occurs in a column. Stainless steel makes up the column. It has an interior diameter of 2-4.6 cm and a length of 5-25 cm (Chawla G and Chaudhary KK, 2019).

5. Detector: According to Chawla G and Chaudhary KK (2019), the detector is able to identify each component that elutes from the column and transform the data into an electrical signal. There are two sorts of detectors that are used: bulk property detectors and specialized detectors. UV-VIS, photo diode array, fluorescence, and mass spectrometric detectors are examples of specific detectors. Refractive index, electrochemical, and light scattering detectors are examples of bulk property detectors (Hamilton RJ, Sewell PA, 1982).

6. Data recording system: The output is recorded as a sequence of peaks, and the computer connected to the display can automatically compute the area beneath each peak (Malviya R, et al., 2010).

Analytical method development: The process of choosing a precise assay technique to determine a formulation's composition is known as analytical method development. The process of demonstrating that an analytical method is appropriate for use in a laboratory is called method development. Analytical techniques must be developed following the ICH's specified protocols and acceptance criteria in GMP and GLP environments. Q2 (R1) recommendations (Chauhan A, et al., 2015).

The following criteria must be met in order to design a method:

Qualified analysts

Instruments-qualified and calibrated

Documented methods

Reliable reference standards

Sample selection and integrity

Change control (Chauhan A, et al., 2015)

The development of analytical methods is beneficial for

- 1) New process and reactions
- 2) New molecule development
- 3) Active ingredients (Macro analysis)
- 4) Residues (Micro analysis)
- 5) Impurity profiling
- 6) Degradation studies
- 7) Herbal products (Chauhan A, et al., 2015)

Procedures for developing a method

1) Standard analyte characterization

- Every piece of information that is known about the analyte and its structure, such as its chemical and physical characteristics, is gathered.
- The 100% pure standard analyte is obtained. Proper storage condition is arranged such as freezer, refrigerator and desiccators.
- Several components are estimated from the sample matrix, their number is taken into account, data is gathered, and the availability of standards for each component is ascertained.
- Only techniques that are appropriate for sample stability—such as spectroscopy, HPLC, GC, MS, etc.—are taken into consideration (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).

2) Method requirements: To determine the analytical figures of advantage, such as linearity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection, limit of quantification, specificity, selectivity, and range, among others, analytical methodology is required (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).

3) Literature survey and prior methodology: By doing a literature review and consulting books, journals, pharmacopoeias, and other sources, all kinds of information on the

analyte—including its physical and chemical characteristics, solubility, manufacture, and associated analytical techniques—are gathered. Automated computerized literature searches from the Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) are also useful for literature surveys (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).

- 4) **Selecting a method:** The information gathered from the literature is used to construct the approach. The approach is being updated as needed. In certain cases, additional equipment is required to replicate, alter, validate, or enhance existing techniques for samples and analytes. In the event that there is no documented method for the analyte in the literature, substances with the same chemical properties and analyte structure are explored (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).
- 5) **Proper instrumental arrangement and initial studies:** It is necessary to set up the required equipment. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are used to verify Installation Qualification (IQ), Operational Qualification (OQ), and Performance Qualification (PQ). For instance, method development is never started using an HPLC column that has already been utilized. Solvents, standard solutions with established concentrations, and the analyte solution are created. Instead of starting with a complicated sample matrix, it is essential to start with a real, recognized standard. It is likely to start working with the actual sample if it is extremely near to the standard (active medication) (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).
- 6) **Optimization:** Rather of employing a trial-and-error method, one parameter is altered at a time and the set of terms is altered throughout optimization. Each case is recorded in a lab notebook, and work has been completed using the systematic approach (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).
- 7) **Proper documentation of analytical figures of merits:** Limit of Detection (LOD), Limit of Quantification (LOQ), linearity, evaluation time, and expenditures are the first established analytical figures of merit. sample preparation, among other things, are recorded (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).
- 8) **Evaluation of method development along with actual samples:** According to Ravisankar P. et al. (2014), the prepared solution for the analyte must be precise, absolute identification of the medication's peak interest apart from all the various matrix components.
- 9) **Determination of percentage recovery of actual sample and demonstration of quantitative sample analysis:** The percentage of authentic, spiked standard analyte recovered in a sample matrix without Analyte is calculated. The capacity to replicate

recovery across samples has been refined. It is not necessary to achieve 100% recovery if the outcomes are repeatable. Only laboratory research is used to confirm the validity of analytical methods. In order to ascertain whether a method is appropriate for its intended application, documenting of such successful research is a fundamental prerequisite (Ravisankar P, et al., 2014).

VALIDATION

The idea of validation was created in the US in 1978. Over time, the idea of validation has expanded to include a variety of tasks, such as the use of analytical techniques to monitor drug quality, chemicals and pharmaceutical goods up to computerized systems for labelling, process control, or clinical trials. It is best to view validation as a fundamental and essential component of cGMP.

The term "validation" refers to the assessment of validity or the process of demonstrating efficacy. Validation is a collaborative effort involving individuals from several plant branches. According to Lavanya G. et al. (2013), method validation is a "process of establishing documented evidence" that offers a high degree of assurance that the product (equipment) will satisfy the specifications of the intended analytical applications.

Importance of validation

- ❖ Assurance of quality
- ❖ Minimal batch failure
- ❖ Reduction in rejections
- ❖ Improved efficiency and productivity
- ❖ Increased output
- ❖ Reduced testing in process and in finished goods (Lavanya G, et al., 2013).

Types of validation

There are four different kinds of validation:

- 1) Equipment validation
 - a. Design Qualification
 - b. Installation Qualification
 - c. Operational Qualification
 - d. Performance Qualification

- 2) Process validation
 - a. Prospective validation
 - b. Retrospective validation
 - c. Concurrent validation
 - d. Revalidation

- 3) Analytical method validation

- 4) Cleaning validation (Lavanya G, et al., 2013)

Analytical techniques that need to be verified

- Identification tests
- Quantitative tests for impurities content
- Limit tests for the control of impurities
- Quantitative analyses of drug samples' active ingredients (Lavanya G, et al., 2013) Steps in method validation.

Steps in method validation

- 1) Create an operational method, validation protocol, or validation master plan for the validation.
- 2) Define the scope, goal and applications of the approach.
- 3) Specify the acceptance criteria and performance specifications.
- 4) Describe experiments for validation.
- 5) Check the equipment's associated performance attributes.
- 6) Qualify materials, such as reagents and standards.
- 7) Conduct experiments prior to validation.
- 8) Modify the approval criteria or procedure parameters if necessary.
- 9) Conduct comprehensive validation studies both internally and externally.
- 10) Create SOPs for the method's routine implementation.
- 11) Establish revalidation standards.
- 12) Specify the kind and frequency of routine Analytical Quality Control (AQC) inspections and/or system appropriateness testing.
- 13) Record validation tests and findings (Lavanya G, et al., 2013).

Method validation parameters (components)

- 1) Accuracy

- 2) Precision
 - 3) Linearity
 - 4) Limit of detection
 - 5) Limit of quantitation
 - 6) Specificity
 - 7) Range
 - 8) Robustness
- 1) Accuracy: The degree to which test findings closely resemble the genuine value is known as accuracy.
 - 2) Precision: The degree of agreement between several measurements made on the same sample is known as precision.

The relative standard deviation is used to express the precision.

Standard deviation/mean $\times 100$ equals %RSD

- 3) Linearity: The capacity of an analytical method to produce a result that is exactly proportionate to the concentration (quantity) of analyte in the sample is known as linearity. The confidence interval surrounding the regression line's slope is used to express linearity.
- 4) Limit Of Detection (LOD): The lowest amount (concentration) of analyte in a sample that may be identified or detected but not measured is known as LOD. A concentration at a given signal is used to express LOD: noise ratio, often 3:1.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{S/SD}$$

- 6) Specificity: The capacity of an analytical method to accurately quantify the analyte in the presence of additional components is known as specificity.

This definition implies the following:

- a. Identification
- b. Purity tests
- c. Assay

- 7) Range: The interval between the upper and lower analyte levels that have been established with a reasonable degree of accuracy, precision, and linearity is known as the method's range. It is calculated using a linear or nonlinear response curve and expressed in the same unit as the test findings.

8) Robustness: The ability of an analytical process to withstand slight changes in method parameters is known as robustness (Vidushi Y and Meenakshi B, 2017).

CONCLUSION

This page provides information on how to create a method, what validation is, why it's important, different kinds of validation, and how to validation procedure and its parameters to demonstrate that the approach is appropriate for the purpose for which it was designed. Identification, purification, and ultimately the qualification of any required medication are the main goals of the development of analytical techniques. The creation of analytical techniques aids in comprehending the crucial process variables and lessening their impact on accuracy and precision. In the pharmaceutical industry, validation is an essential method used to guarantee that high-quality work is completed in the process that supports the creation of medicines cinema and merchandise.

REFERENCES

1. Kenkel J. Analytical Chemistry for Technicians. Lewis Publishers, 2003.
2. Kissinger PT. Instant Notes: Analytical Chemistry. Clin Chem., 2002; 48(12): 2303.
3. Harvey D. Modern analytical chemistry. McGraw-Hill, 2000.
4. Ravisankar P, Navya CN, Pravallika D, Sir DN. A review on step-by -step analytical method validation. IOSR J Pharm., 2015; 5(10): 7-19.
5. Jeffery GH. Textbook of quantitative chemical analysis. Longman, 1989.
6. Chatwal GR, Anand SK. Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis. Himalaya Publishing House, 2002.
7. Kumar S. Spectroscopy of organic compounds. Cosmic rays., 2006; 10: 4.
8. Luxminarayan L, Sharma N, Viswas A, khinchi MP. A review on chromatography techniques. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, 2017; 1-8.
9. Chawla G, Chaudhary KK. A review of HPLC technique covering its pharmaceutical, environmental, forensic, clinical and other applications. Int J Pharm Chem Anal., 2019; 6(2): 27-39.
10. Vidushi Y, Meenakshi B. A review on HPLC method development and validation. Res J Life Sci., 2017; 2(6): 178.
11. McPolin O As introduction to HPLC for pharmaceutical analysis. Lulu., 2009.
12. Malviya R, Bansal V, Pal OP, Sharma PK. High performance liquid chromatography: a short review. J Glob Pharma Technol, 2010; 2(5): 22-26.

13. Jena AK. HPLC: highly accessible instrument in pharmaceutical industry for erective method development. *Pharm Anal Acta.*, 2011; 3.
14. Agilent Technologies. *The LC Handbook Guide to LC Columns and Method Development*. Agilent Technologies, 2016; 16.
15. Hamilton RJ, Sewell PA. *Introduction to high performance liquid chromatography*. Springer, 1982; 1-12.
16. Chauhan A, Mittu B, Chauhan P. analytical method development and validation: a concise review. *J anal Bioanal Tech.*, 2015; 6(1): 1-5.
17. Ravisankar P, Gowthami S, Rao GD. A review on analytical method development. *Indian J Res Pharm Biotech*, 2014; 2(3): 11.83.
18. Lavanya G, Sunil M, Eswarudu MM, Eswaraiah MC, Harisudha K, Spandana BN. Analytical method validation: An updated review. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2013; 4(4): 1280.